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A Novel Technique of Utilization of Common Mode Voltage as an Energy Source

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Abstract

The domestic supply socket consists of three terminals namely live, neutral and earth. The potential difference between live and neutral is almost of constant magnitude while the P.D between neutral and earth should be ideally zero. But practically it is not zero. A small PD exists between the neutral and earth terminal due to the voltage drop across the resistance of the neutral wire. Its value ranges from .1-6V depends on the loads connected and the amount of unbalance between the phases. The voltage is maximum at peak hours at midday. It is small in the morning and evening. Till now there has been no practical usage of this small potential difference. Experiments were carried out to find the credibility of this small voltage for practical applications. The most important field that has been found is electrolysis. Strong and weak electrolytes require different circuits for proper utilization of the NE potential. Construction and characteristics of such circuits (making use of the small potential difference between neutral and earth terminals) have been dealt with in this paper in detail.

Key words: Neutral; Earth; Potential; Electrolysis; Current

Abbreviations

NE- Neutral to earth. PD-Potential Difference

Introduction

Indian domestic electricity supply is designed to operate at 230V-50Hz single phase A.C. So under ideal conditions the potential difference between live and neutral is 230V. The earth terminal is provided for safety. Normally every electrical appliance that we use for domestic purposes can be run using only live and neutral wire, with neutral serving as the return path for current. The potential difference between neutral and earth should be theoretically being zero. But under actual conditions the case is some what different. In reality the neutral wire possesses some resistance, however small. When current flows a potential drop occurs across it which is given by $V_{Drop} = IR$. On the other hand the potential of the earth terminal is always zero. Hence, under practical conditions a voltage must exist between neutral and earth terminal. Since in electrical wiring system switch is always made in the live wire, switching off the circuit removes the live wire but not the neutral wire. So voltage exists between neutral and earth terminals even if the switch is off. However, this voltage drop is not constant. It varies over a wide range and may be as large as 6V or as small as .1V. But what ever might be the case a finite small value is always present. Some engineers say that

measurement of this small voltage using a multimeter is indicative of the condition as to whether the earthing system is working properly or not. Earthing system maintains the potential of the earth terminal at zero. So if a potential difference is obtained between neutral and earth terminals, it may be inferred that earthing system is proper. But many are opposed to this idea. The opposition stands justified owing to the following points:-

- At off peak hours the neutral voltage may be very close to zero. As a result potential difference is zero and it indicates faulty earthing.
- The P.D may be a few mV which may not be detected in case the instrument is not very sensitive.
- But the question that riles us is that can this potential difference between neutral and earth of any use. The easiest answer found on the internet is that a LED can glow with this voltage.

Keeping these questions in mind various experiments were performed to put the neutral to earth voltage to use. The results yielded show that the most significant use lies in the electrolysis technology.

The subsequent sections of this paper deal with the same.

Materials and Reagents Required

- IN4007 diodes
- Electrolyte capacitor 4700 μ F-25V
- Oil capacitor (used in ceiling fans)
- Transformer 230/12V 3A
- Transformer 230/4.5-0-4.5V (Centre tapped) 300mA
- Carbon resistors 1K, 47K, 230K
- NPN transistor having D.C current gain of $\beta=50$ (NPN 2N5686)
- Sensitive digital multimeter
- Water
- Acetic acid
- Sodium chloride (common salt)
- Dry cells 1.5V
- A variable resistor
- Sensitive digital multimeter

Experimental Diagrams

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Experimental

Before proceeding further with experiments the variation of neutral to earth voltage, over a period of 12 hours from 9 am to 9 pm was studied. The interval between two successive readings was 30 minutes. Accordingly a graph was plotted. From the graph it is quite evident that the NE voltage is the highest at the peak hours. But the voltage has a low value nevertheless. So it cannot be used for high voltage applications like domestic lighting, fan, etc. On an average 1.5V is available. This voltage may be utilized in the following two

Figure 4. Graph 1

ways:—

- It may be directly utilized at an average value of 1.5V (very similar to a single dry cell).
- It can be stepped up to a higher value (say 40V) and then it may be put to use.

So experiments were designed to test both methods.

Experiment 1

This was carried out with an attempt of making direct use of the NE voltage. So the neutral to earth voltage was fed directly to the terminals of a bridge rectifier (using 4 diodes). A 4700 μ F capacitor was connected across the output terminals. The D.C voltage was used to cause electrolysis of strong NaCl solution. After about 45 seconds of closing the switch strong bubbling at the cathode is observed. The intensity of bubbles was same throughout the entire interval of the experiment. Normal characteristics of electrolysis of brine using a battery (pure D.C source) are observed. A characteristic curve of D.C voltage across load to the A.C voltage across the NE terminals was plotted. The same experiment was repeated using pure

Figure 5. Graph 2

water as an electrolyte. As expected, it took longer for electrolysis to start. The bubbling was also not as intense as observed in the case of NaCl solution. Acetic acid was also tried as the electrolyte. Hence a comparison was obtained between a very strong electrolyte (NaCl), a moderately strong electrolyte (acetic acid) and a very weak electrolyte (pure water).

Experiment 2

This was performed with a view to step up the voltage between neutral and earth. Accordingly the apparatus described in figure 1 was set up. The NE voltage was fed to the LV side of a 230-12V,3A transformer and the output from the HV terminal (230V side) was rectified using a simple rectifier bridge (using four diodes). A 4700 μ F

capacitor was put in parallel with the D.C side. Pure water was used as the load. Hydrogen bubbles were evolved from the cathode. A graph was plotted to describe the variation of the D.C output voltage with the variation in NE voltage.

Figure 6. Graph 3

Experiment 3

The above experiment was repeated using another transformer rated 230V 4.5-0-4.5V (refer to figure no.2), and this time a carbon resistor was used as a load. But it was then noticed that the circuit exhibited an extremely poor regulation. So no capacitor was put in parallel with the load. A 230KΩ was used as the load. The variation of output D.C voltage with a variation of input A.C voltage was plotted. Water

Figure 7. Graph 4

or any other such electrolyte could not be used in this transformer because of extremely poor regulation.

Experiment 4

A half wave voltage doubler circuit was connected to the output of the HT side of a 12/230V transformer with the NE voltage fed into the LT side. As expected the no load voltage was double the peak voltage. But a problem with this circuit was recognized. The regulation was extremely poor. A 47KΩ resistor was connected to the output. The voltage at once dropped from 42V to .4V. Hence this circuit cannot be used for practical applications. When 47K was replaced by a 230K resistor a voltage of 1.6V was recorded.

Experiment 5

It is well known that a CE amplifier using a BJT is capable of providing a very high current gain. The amplified current remains almost constant for a particular range of collector resistances. So with a reasonable value of current gain a large amplification of base current is possible.

Keeping these in view, a setup was constructed as shown in figure

Table 1

Base Voltage (V)	Base Current (mA)	Collector Voltage (V)	Collector Current (mA)
3	1	30.6	50
3	1.5	30.6	74
3	2	30	100
3	2.5	29	120
3	3	29.4	140
3	3.5	28	160
3	4	27.9	170
3	4.5	27.8	175
3	5	27.6	175.5
3	5.5	27.5	175.6
3	6	27.5	175.6

3. The transistor was a common npn transistor with a current amplification factor of 50. The base-emitter circuit was biased using a 3V dry cell (two 1.5V dry cells in series). A resistor was used to vary the base current I_B . The collector circuit was biased using the stepped up D.C voltage from a 230-12V, 3A transformer. For collector resistance, pure water was used. A curve of base current Vs collector current was plotted. The following table gives more detailed

Figure 8. Graph 5

description of the circuit parameters.

Experiment 6

The neutral to earth voltage was input to the LV sides of the two transformers mentioned in the previous experiments. The output from the H.V side (230V side) was joined in series. The output of the first transformer was 42V while that of the other was 100V (due to higher transformation ratio). In series addition mode the output was 135V while that in series opposition was 56V. At that time the NE voltage was 1.45V. But when a 47KΩ resistor was connected to the output, the terminal voltage dropped to about .9V in both cases. So, though voltage 'magnification' (totally different from magnification using a transistor) was possible, the amplified voltage could not be put to any use. Also the figures indicate that the resultant voltage is slightly less than the algebraic sum (or difference) of the individual voltage. This must have occurred due to the phase difference between the constituent voltages. Again the phase difference is due to the unequal X/R ratio of the individual transformers.

Experiment 7

A solution of acetic acid was electrolyzed using the voltage on the 230V side with the 12V side fed from the NE voltage. The switch was kept closed for 12 hours and a solution of bluish green copper acetate was obtained. The hydrogen obtained at the cathode was collected in an inverted test tube by downward displacement of water. If a little sodium chloride is added to the solution, the terminal voltage gets

lower but the yield gets faster. But if a pure solution of copper acetate is desired, use of sodium chloride or any such material should be avoided.

Experiment 8

In this experiment a brief study of the power supplying capability of the NE voltage was made. A 230-12V/3A transformer was used for this purpose. The LV side was fed with the NE voltage and the HT side was connected to a variable resistor. A curve of current supplied by the HT to the terminal voltage was plotted. From the

Figure 9. Graph 6

curve it is evident that as the load increases the terminal voltage decreases. The variation of voltage with load current is almost linear (shown by a trend line).

Observations

The voltage that exists between neutral and earth terminals due to imbalance in phase voltages is not very high in magnitude and there is a large variation of the voltage with time during the day. Direct application of this voltage in the rectified form (D.C) causes electrolysis of strong electrolytes like sodium chloride. Stepping up of this voltage is easily accomplished by an ordinary transformer with the NE voltage fed to the LV side. It is possible to get voltage magnitudes of 30-40V on open circuit. But when the circuit is closed, even for a high value of load resistance, there is a marked drop in terminal voltage due to the high impedance of the transformer winding. A voltage doubler also produces a marked increase in terminal voltage, but on no load only. The circuit is totally ineffective when a load is connected. The percentage regulation of the circuit is very poor and varies with the type of the transformer used. A circuit using a transformer is of use when weak electrolytes like acetic acid are electrolyzed. Dilute solutions of copper acetate can be easily prepared. Here the raw materials are only copper wire and dilute acetic acid (vinegar serves the purpose well). However, the time required is large. The power available is low (due to low voltage and current) & is not constant throughout.

Results and Discussions

- There exists a finite potential difference between the neutral and earth terminals which arises due to unbalanced currents in the different phases of a three phase system.
- This potential difference is not constant & varies during the day, being the maximum at peak hours
- The magnitude of the potential difference is very small.
- The voltage between the neutral and earth terminals show the characteristics of ordinary 230V-50Hz A.C voltage, i.e. it can be stepped up, rectified and filtered.
- This voltage is suitable for low power applications (in the range of a few mW)
- For loads having resistances higher than $25K\Omega$, ordinary step up transformers can step up this voltage and perform useful work. A typical application is electrolysis of pure water.

- For resistances below $1K\Omega$, the regulation of an ordinary transformer becomes very poor. For e.g. electrolysis of NaCl solution. A specially designed transformer must be used in such cases.
- Strong electrolytes may be electrolyzed using direct application of neutral to earth voltage using a simple bridge rectifier and a capacitor filter. There is no need for transformers. The capacitor must have a large value of capacitance (above $2200\mu F$)
- The output voltages of transformers may be 'added up' or 'subtracted' using the proper polarity connections. This is just as in case of ordinary A.C circuits.
- A BJT having good current amplification factor in conjunction with a transformer may make very good use of the neutral to earth voltage. For best results the base emitter circuit must be biased using a battery. Zinc-carbon dry cells serve very well.
- For using a bridge rectifier circuit an inductor filter should never be used because it would make the voltage regulation even worse.
- Use of the surplus energy provided by the neutral to earth voltage allows the slow synthesis of compounds of weak acids like copper acetate from a solution of acetic acid.

The NE voltage being low requires special treatment before it can be put to use. The probable solution lies in the use of a step up transformer. But the circuit works for high resistances only. For low resistances the transformer impedance becomes very large compared to that of the load. This is the problem associated with NaCl solution. So maximum potential drop occurs across the transformer winding and the voltage across the solution is low (about 1V).

The transformer should be specially designed with transformation ratio of 1:5 so as to step up .5V to 2.5V. The windings should be made of high grade copper, so as to have minimum winding resistance and hence the minimum drop. For high resistivity solutions a current amplifier must be used. As 15mA-20mA is enough to cause electrolysis of solutions the choice of the amplifying transistor should not be difficult. If a transistor amplifier has to be used, the BE bias may be provided using a separate battery while the CE bias may be provided by the transformer itself. Under all circumstances common emitter configuration must be used (due to large current gain).

Applications

So far as practical applications are concerned, electrolysis seems to be the best available option. This is because of the following reasons:

- Strong electrolytes require a very small voltage, sometimes less than 1V to sustain the reaction.
- Moderate and weak electrolytes require 2.5-3V which may be easily available from a transformer

Conclusion

The energy crisis is ever increasing. The neutral to earth terminal voltage which arises due to unbalanced loading in three phase distribution system is left ignored. But this potential difference between neutral and earth terminals, however small, has the capability to provide energy for low power applications. In this paper stress has been laid on electrolysis technology as a low power* application. The only disadvantage is that the voltage is very low except at peak hours. Also, variations may occur from place to place.

The NE voltage which is considered as wastage may prove immensely useful if utilized using properly designed circuits (examples discussed in the earlier sections). This provides surplus energy in addition to our daily demand, which has the ability to perform work. As distribution systems can never be perfectly balanced, the NE voltage will always exist. It will provide sufficient energy for small scale production of gases like hydrogen, oxygen, and chemicals derived from weak acids like copper acetate.

*This is totally different from industrial electrolysis, which relies on high current and high power applications.

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